

Pupils' Self-Esteem and Emotional Intelligence as Correlate of Their Psychological Well-Being in Primary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study determined pupils' self-esteem and emotional intelligence as correlate of their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level. Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 37,190 basic five pupils in Anambra State. A sample size of 817 pupils was draw for the study using multistage sampling procedure. Three sets of instruments: "Self-Esteem Scale (SES)", "Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS)" and "Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts who are lecturers, two from the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.79 for SES, 0.76 for EIS and 0.81 PWS. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and t-test of correlation was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a strong and significant relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that there is a strong relationship between pupils' emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school counselor should identify and render professional supports to pupils with low emotional intelligence to help them to effectively manage their emotions in positive ways to improve their psychological well-being.

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Introduction

Education is an instrument for transmitting social norms, values and developing skills of individuals to make them responsible and productive members of the society. It is also the means for grooming the personality of individuals and providing information that prepare them for the careers which they intends to pursue in future. Amobi, Onye and Anyaogu (2024) opined that education is an instrument for improving knowledge, talents, potentials and skills of individuals towards enabling them contribute to sustained improvement of personal wellbeing in particular and development of the society at large. Furthermore, they stated that it equally enables individuals to develop critical thinking ability personal values for purposeful living in the society and appreciate/cultivate dignity of labour. The first stage of education in Nigeria is basic level.

Basic education is the fundamental learning opportunity offered to pupils to lay solid foundation for life-long learning. Anisiobi, Wadi and Ushang (2023) opined that basic education is the foundational level where students acquire basic numeric and literacy skills. The duration for the completion of basic education is nine years. Basic education embraces early care given to children aged 0-4 years and nine years of formal schooling. To buttress this, Adamu and Adebisi (2023) noted that basic education encompasses Early Child Care and Development Education which is segmented into ages 0-4 years, situated in daycare or creches, fully in the hands of the private sector and social development services, whilst ages 5-6 are within the formal education sector. The pupils who have the belief to succeed in basic schools possess high self-esteem.

Self-esteem is demonstrated through high confidence and belief in one's ability to successfully execute tasks. Udeh and Ezeokafor (2022) defined self-esteem as a feeling of self-competence and self-worth that could enable one to successfully execute tasks. It is a stable sense of personal worth and capacity to face a given challenge. Okafor, Nwikpo, Anierobi and Onwuka (2023) defined self-esteem as an internal belief system that an individual possesses about his or her worth. According to Illoakasia (2021), self-esteem is a person's overall evaluation of his or her own worth. The author added that individuals with positive self-esteem feel more confident and tend to worry less about rejection than those with negative self-esteem. Similarly, Umar, Tijjani, Hamza and Umara (2021) pointed out that individuals with high self-esteem are more confident, happy, and self-respecting, while people with low self-esteem are likely to be anxious, lacking self-confidence and self-criticism. Also, Omisola, Mosaku and Fatunbi (2022) noted that learners with low self-esteem feel unworthy, incapable and incompetent compared with those with a normal or high self-esteem.

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and control one's mood. Oparaugo and Ebenebe (2021) described emotional intelligence as the ability to identify and manage one's emotions and that of others. Pupils with high emotional intelligence could easily cope to the demands of academic tasks in primary schools. Agu and Nwankwo (2019) noted that the basic components of emotional intelligence include: self-awareness (understanding their moods emotions and drives), self-regulation, (regulate one's emotions and behaviour) interpersonal skills (empathetic and cooperative), adaptability (capacity to cope with the environment), mood and motivation. Emotional intelligence is the recognition and regulation of feeling and reaction to mood. According to Prasad and Lone (2023), emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive emotion, use emotion to evoke thought, comprehend emotion, and regulation of emotions and related feelings.

Psychological well-being is the feeling of contentment with one's mental state. Prasad and Lone (2023) described psychological well-being as a state of optimal functioning and satisfaction with one's life. Psychological well-being is positively connected to physical and emotional state of pupils. Psychological well-being is defined by Enwere and Mbakwe (2021), as a positive feeling which is associated with happy, healthy, socially connected and purposeful life. It is peaceful state of mind and emotional among pupils. Omisola, Mosaku and Fatunbi (2022) defined psychological wellbeing as the condition of being content with life and having an abundance of positive emotions. It is the absence of depression, tension and anxiety among learners. Nwankwo, Okechi and Nweke (2015) noted that psychological well-being is related to better physical health and normal cognitive functioning. Psychological wellbeing is the condition in which pupils have sound mental health.

Some primary school pupils seem to display of emotional neglect, anxiety, poor mood and bad mood which is probably associated with psychological well-being. Adegboyega (2019) noted that pupils display emotional disturbances, personality disorder, low self-confidence and poor attention in classroom which make them to perform below expectation in primary schools in Nigeria. Some pupils who experience psychological disorder tend to engage in maladaptive behaviours such as anger, fighting and noise-making in the classroom.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine pupils' self-esteem and emotional intelligence as correlate of their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. Pupils' self-esteem as correlate of their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.
2. Pupils' emotional intelligence as correlate of their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between pupils' emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between pupils' emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 37,190 basic five pupils in Anambra State. A sample size of 817 pupils was drawn for the study using multistage sampling procedure. In the first stage, simple random sampling technique without replacement was used to draw three education authorities for the study. In the second stage, proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to draw 817 pupils from schools in selected education authorities. Three sets of instruments: "Self-Esteem Scale (SES)", "Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS)" and "Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS)" were used for data collection. SES contains 12 items, EIS had 15 items and PWS contained 17 items. All the items of the three instruments are structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts who are lecturers, two from the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.79 for SES, 0.76 for EIS and 0.81 PWS.

The instruments were administered by the researchers and four research assistants. A total of 817 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 801 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98 percent return rate. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and t-test of correlation was used to test hypotheses. The

research questions was interpreted using the coefficient r and the size of the relationship recommended by Alsagr (2021), as follows

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p -value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p -value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between pupils’ self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the Pupils’ Self-Esteem and their Psychological Well-Being

Variables	N	Pupils’ Self-Esteem	Self- Psychological Well-being	Remarks
Pupils’ Self-Esteem	801	1.00	.725	Strong Positive
Psychological Well-being	801	.725	1.00	

Table 1 indicated that the Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) obtained was 0.725. This shows that there is a strong relationship between pupils’ self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between pupils’ emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the Pupils’ Emotional Intelligence and their Psychological Well-Being

Variables	n	Pupils’ Emotional Intelligence	Psychological Well-being	Remarks
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Table 4 indicated that the p-value of 0.00 is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between pupils' emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that there is a strong relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Enwere and Mbakwe (2021) which showed that self esteem was a strong predictor of psychological well-being of senior secondary school adolescents. This disagreed with the finding of Omisola, Mosaku and Fatunbi (2022) which showed that there was a weak negative relationship between self-esteem and psychological wellbeing of adolescents. The disagreement with the finding could be connected to difference in geographical location. The possible explanation for this finding is that pupils with high self-esteem have positive belief in their abilities to handle difficult situations and copy with stress which could account for the strong relationship with their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Self-esteem makes pupils to worry less about academic tasks which improve their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. It was also found that there is significant relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. This is in line with the finding of Enwere and Mbakwe (2021) which revealed that self-esteem was a significant predictor of psychological well-being of senior secondary school adolescents. This also supported the finding of Nwankwo, Okechi and Nweke (2015) which indicated that self-esteem had significant relationship with psychological well-being of student athletes. The pupils with positive self-esteem are often prepared to handle depression or any difficult academic tasks in primary schools in Anambra State.

The result of the study showed that there is a strong relationship between pupils' emotional intelligence and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. This affirmed the finding of Shaheen and Shaheen (2016) which showed that there was strong correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. This is contrary to the finding of Prasad and Lone (2023) which revealed that there was a very weak significant correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. This also disagreed with the finding of Rathakrishnan et al (2019) which showed that there was moderate correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. The difference in geographical location and time span could be responsible for the disagreement with the finding. This showed that high emotional intelligence of pupils is connected to their strong psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Pupils with high emotional intelligence have the abilities to cope with academic pressure which might be responsible for

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strong relationship with their psychological well-being. Emotional intelligence leads to better social adjustment among pupils which is crucial to their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Further result showed that there is significant relationship between pupils' self-esteem and their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Shaheen and Shaheen (2016) which indicated that there was significant correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. This also agreed with the finding of Seyed, Hossein, Mohammad and Morteza (2014) which showed that there was significant relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of employees. This contradicted the finding of Prasad and Lone (2023) which indicated that there was no significant correlation between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. Pupils with high emotional intelligence feel comfortable in performing academic tasks which could explain the significant relationship with their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that pupils' self-esteem and emotional intelligence are strong and significant correlate of their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Pupils with high self-esteem and emotional intelligence tend to have positive mood and possess abilities to handle anxiety which contribute to their psychological well-being in primary schools in Anambra State. Pupils with high self-esteem and emotional intelligence have confidence and abilities to manage difficult tasks and their emotions in positive ways to prevent mental disorder in primary schools.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Headteachers should lay emphasizes on issues regarding self-esteem during the orientation programme of newly admitted pupils to help develop self-confidence in abilities to successfully carry out academic activities and improve their psychological well-being.
2. School counselor should identify and render professional supports to pupils with low emotional intelligence to help them to effectively manage their emotions in positive ways to improve their psychological well-being.

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